
METHODS OF WRITING AND WORKING WITH PR TEXT – PRESS REALISE

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the main approaches to the classification of one of the PR texts press release. A well-written press release could open doors for well networking with journalists. The main purpose of this article is to provide theoretical and practical material necessary for the formation of students of skills and abilities of writing press release of different genre affiliation and their analysis in terms of communicative effectiveness. In this article discussed writing a successful release so that your research has a better chance to be covered by the mass media.

Keywords: mass media, PR, press release, PR texts, press release rules, PR-specialists.

Mass media define everything in modern human life. What he eats, wears, looks, where he works, etc. Behind all this is the great work of PR specialists of various organizations and firms. The success of the promotion of new products, news events, advertising campaigns, as well as effective interactions with the media largely depends on a well-written PR text.

Every day, PR-specialists send out a lot of texts for building relationships of his company with the media, partners, customers, shareholders, employees and other groups of the public, but far from always these texts serve as an effective tool for the formation and development of the image of an organization or person, since written in an unprofessional manner. Teaching students how to write PR texts correctly is one of the tasks professional training of specialists in advertising and communications with the public. However, despite the fact that in recent years a significant number of textbooks and manuals on the theory and practice of public relations have been published, still there is a lack of educational and methodological literature devoted to the problem of teaching students of communication specialties to write PR-texts of different genres.

Particular attention is paid to those genres of PR-texts, in the creation of which a PR-specialist experiences difficulties due to their insufficient coverage in educational literature (e.g. genre of media statement) [L.V.Balaxonskaya, 2015.].

Basic PR-texts are divided into primary and secondary. Primary texts are texts that originate from the basic or technological subject of PR; it is the primary texts that form the core of the corpus of PR texts. They go directly to public groups in its original form. Secondary texts are communicated to public groups indirectly, through mass media.

Press release is the main genre of PR text, providing Mass media up-to-date operational information about the news event in the activities of the subject of PR. In domestic practice PR is sometimes found replacing the foreign word “press release” Russian equivalents “information message” or “information for the press”, but the first term is the most established.

Post-release, in our opinion, can be used in PR-communications only in those cases when the subject returns to the news already published some time ago to give some comments from today’s position.

Depending on the content of M.Gundarin and E.Gundarin the following types of press releases are suggested: press release - a sensation; press release - portrait; press release - a curious fact; press release - question (problem); press release - comment; press release - quote book, etc. [Gundarin, Gundarina, 2013:15].

Press release structure: a header that includes a logo, the name of the organization (it is possible to indicate the address), the name of the PR structure, the contact information (name and surname of the contact person, phone number, e-mail, website address); date of distribution; name of the genre (press release); title; lead - first paragraph; main text.

The title of the press release should contain “hard” news, answer questions: when? where? who? what? The title indicates the news event (topic) and the subject of PR, as well as where and when the event happened or will happen. At the end of the title point is not set. The press release lead contains soft news, responds to questions: when? where? who? what? why? how? Lead in many ways repeats the content of the title, but more fully describes news.

The main text of the press release contains more detailed information about the news event, about the subject of PR; indicate details, specific facts and figures are given. Every paragraph a press release should be auto semantic, relatively independent in terms of content. As a rule, a press release quotes the first (official)

person or a well-known expert in this field, in which a commentary is given on the described event, its assessment is expressed. The quotation is usually made in the form of a sentence with direct speech and must be attributed. To introduce direct speech, verbs with the meaning messages: said, and informed. When making a quote to indicate the words of the author, the PR specialist must use other words or phrases to avoid unnecessary repetitions: stated, noted, believes, emphasized, stated, convinced, emphasized, reminded, promised, explained, concluded, suggested, etc. Their choice will be depend on the content of the quote. Quoted words should be enclosed in quotation marks. Functions of a quote in a press release:

- indication of the reliability of information;
- image-making of the author of the quote;
- giving the news a “human” character [Krivonosov, Filatova, Shishkina, 2010: 216].

The quotation may contain elements of subjective modality and means of expressing the personal beginning; it is possible the use of expressive means (epithets, metaphors, inversions, parcels, etc.). All of these tools make it easy perception of a quote, give it individuality [Diane Scherzler M.A.].

Some researchers believe that a press release may contain not one, but several quotes from different speakers commenting on the described event in different ways. Subsequently, from a series of quotations, the journalist will be able to select those them, which most of all correspond to the topic and nature of the material. Even the headline can be in the form of a quote. Press release, but in this case the author is quoted in the title words should be well known not only to journalists, but also wide audience.

The press release may also contain additional, background information about the company or its products, that is, it may contain a background element. But if the volume of the press release large enough, then this background information is better transfer to applications - fact sheet or more detailed backgrounder text that will be sent along with the press release.

In terms of composition, the text of a press release is built according to the inverted pyramid model, when the most important information is presented in the first paragraphs, and the less important in subsequent paragraphs. This is done so that the journalist could easily shorten the text by simply removing the last phrases. In addition, the presentation of the most important information at the beginning press

release increases the chances that the text will interest the journalist, be read to the end and, possibly, be used as the basis for writing an article or some other material.

The style of writing a press release is distinguished by dryness of presentation, logic, sequence of listing facts. It lacks means of expressing subjective modality and personal beginning, expressive means of language (with the exception of quotations) are not used.

Press release rules:

- The text of the press release is printed on a letterhead with corporate identity elements (logo, font, color, etc.).
- Be sure to indicate the date of distribution and contact information: phone, e-mail, company website, last name and first name of the contact person, recently links to the group are also given social media companies.
- The volume of the press release is one page of an A4 sheet, size 12–14, one and a half intervals. Sometimes a two-page press release is possible.
- Margins and paragraph indents must be respected in order to to make it easier for the journalist to edit the text.
- Font highlights and underlining are not recommended (only the title and lead are printed in bold). [L.V.Balaxonskaya, 2015:69]

In conclusion, press releases are a fairly well-known method of reaching journalists and grabbing an editor’s interest. One of their benefits is that one press release can simultaneously reach thousands of journalists. The fact that this idea is shared by tens of thousands of other scientists and press secretaries is a drawback. Editors get hundreds of press releases every day, and hundreds of them are immediately discarded.

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